

EFFECTS OF 1.0% GLUCOSE INTAKE ON TEAR PRODUCTION AND TEAR STABILITY IN DRY EYE SYNDROME

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339781>

Keywords

Dry Eye Syndrome, Glucose Intake, Tear Production, Tear Stability, TBUT, Schirmer Test, Ocular Surface, Euglycemic Subjects

Article History

Received: 20 August 2025

Accepted: 29 September 2025

Published: 13 October 2025

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: A common ophthalmological disorder known as dry eye syndrome (DES) is characterized by ocular irritation and unstable tear films. There is growing evidence that tear dynamics and systemic glucose levels are related.

OBJECTIVE: This study investigates the effect of 1.0% oral glucose consumption on the stability and generation of tears in DES patients.

METHODOLOGY: A quasi-experimental investigation was conducted with 70 euglycemic individuals aged 18-38. Initial assessments of tear film stability (TBUT) and tear generation (Schirmer test) were noted. Tests were repeated at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes after participants had a 1.0% glucose solution. SPSS version 26 was used to analyze the data.

RESULTS: The results demonstrated that both tear production and tear stability were significantly affected following the intake of 1.0% glucose in euglycemic individuals with dry eye syndrome. Tear production declined from a baseline mean of 13.60 mm to a minimum of 10.51 mm at 60

minutes post-consumption, before rising steadily to reach 14.49 mm at 120 minutes. Similarly,

tear stability decreased to a low of 4.60 seconds at 60 minutes and improved to 7.01 seconds by

120 minutes. Repeated measures ANOVA confirmed these changes were statistically significant

($p < 0.001$). These findings suggest a transient disruption followed by recovery in tear film

dynamics after glucose ingestion.

CONCLUSION: A biphasic pattern in tear dynamics, with an initial drop followed by a compensatory reaction, is suggested by the short-term effects of a 1.0% glucose intake. These results support the significance of glucose regulation in the management of DES by highlighting the ocular surface's sensitivity to systemic metabolic alterations.

INTRODUCTION

Dry Eye Syndrome (DES) is a common condition in ophthalmology, characterized by discomfort, blurred vision, and an unstable tear film, often linked to tear film hyperosmolarity and inflammation (Qu Jh et al; 2017). In clinical settings, dry eye is more commonly reported by diabetic patients compared to other corneal symptoms associated with diabetes. Among the proposed mechanisms underlying dry eye syndrome, dry eye caused by diabetes specifically exhibits key features such as ocular surface inflammation and injury, neurosensory abnormalities, and tear film instability and hyperosmolarity (Kesarwani D, et al; 2017). The tear film is a thin, fluid layer that coats the ocular surface and serves as the eye's interface with the external environment. It plays a crucial role in maintaining ocular comfort and provides mechanical, environmental, and immune protection. Additionally, it supports the health of the corneal and conjunctival epithelium and forms a smooth, refractive surface essential for clear vision (Dartt DA; 2024). The tear film, which is essential for preserving the health and function of the cornea and conjunctiva, is composed of three layers: lipid, aqueous, and mucin. The outermost lipid layer, produced by the meibomian glands, is particularly crucial (Meng F, et al; 2025). It prevents tear evaporation and serves as a barrier against environmental irritants. This layer consists of a complex mixture of fatty acids and wax esters secreted by the meibomian glands (Yazdani M; 2023). Diabetes mellitus is a significant risk factor for dry eye syndrome (DES), which is caused by mechanisms such as peripheral nerve damage, impaired insulin signaling, microvascular dysfunction, and disturbances in fluid and osmotic homeostasis (Zhang X, et al; 2026). Patients with both type 1 and type 2 diabetes have significantly lower tear function than non-diabetics, and poorer glycemic management (higher HbA1c) is related with more severe dysfunction (Kuo et al., 2022; Kaiserman et al., 2005; more investigations). Although inadequate blood sugar control is known to worsen DES symptoms, the therapeutic effect of tight glucose

regulation on reversing or curing DES is less well understood.

This study aims to assess whether improved blood glucose control in diabetics affects dry eye symptoms, using the OSDI, tear film osmolarity, TBUT, and the Schirmer test.

Methodology

It was a Quasi-experimental study. Data was collected from the THQ hospital, Nowshera Virkan. The sample size was 70 patients. Non-probability convenient Sampling Technique was used. The total duration of the study was about 4 months. Both genders between the age 18-38 Years were included. They were euglycemic patients with no previous medication history that causes dry eye and no previous ocular surgical history. Systemic disease & ocular diseases/trauma, prolonged Screen users, diabetic or pre-diabetic people, people with Stevens-Johnson syndrome and Sjogren syndrome were excluded.

In this experimental study evaluated the effects of 1.0% glucose intake on tear production and tear film stability in individuals with dry eye syndrome, data collection followed a structured and standardized protocol. The patients were between 18-38 years because after 18 years, structures are almost completed, and after 38 years, changes like presbyopia occur. Patients with no ocular surgical history and any medication history that causes dry eye were included. Before glucose administration, baseline measurements were recorded without the use of topical anesthesia to preserve the natural tear reflex. Tear film stability was assessed using the Tear Break-Up Time method: Followed a gentle application of a fluorescein strip moistened with sterile saline to the inferior conjunctival sac, the subject was to blink. A slit lamp biomicroscope fitted with a cobalt blue filter was used to quantify, in seconds, the time between the final full blink and the emergence of the first dry spot on the corneal surface. Tear production was evaluated using Schirmer I the lateral part of the lower eyelid used test strips margin of each eye for 5 minutes under ambient conditions, with the wetted length recorded in millimeters. Followed the completion

of baseline TBUT and Schirmer tests, participants were orally consume a preprepared 1.0% glucose solution. Repeat measurements of TBUT and Schirmer test was taken at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes after consumption using the same procedures and environmental conditions to ensure consistency and reliability. Each session was conducted under standardized lighting, temperature, and humidity to minimize variability. All readings were performed by the same trained examiner to reduce inter-observer bias, and data was documented immediately after each measurement interval.

All of the data gathered from the study participants was put into statistical software, i.e., the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 26). Appropriate descriptive statistics were calculated for the nature of the variables

Results

There were 70 participants in the study, ranging in age from 19 to 38. 19–23 years old accounted

for 32.86% of the total, followed by 34–38 years old (25.71%), 29–33 years old (22.86%), and 24–28 years old (18.57%). The distribution of genders was roughly equal, with 33 women (47.14%) and 37 men (52.86%).

After intake of 1% glucose, patient tear production was measured at baseline, 30, 60, 90, and 120. It indicates that the estimated marginal means of tear production at baseline was normal mean \pm 13.60(21.69%) after 30 mint tear production decrease to mean \pm 11.58(18.46%) , after one hour it was mean \pm 10.51 (16.76%), half an hour tear stability again start to regain mean of \pm 12.53(19.98) , and finally after two hour tear stability mean was \pm 14.49(23.10).

It is displayed in a profile plot. After initially declining to a minimum at 60 minutes, tear stability recovers to baseline levels by 90 minutes and shows response to dryness by excessive production of tear within 2 hour.

Tear stability declined from baseline to 60 minutes, peaking at 60 minutes (4.603), then gradually increasing until it reached its maximum at 120 minutes (7.006), indicating a gradual recovery.

In both eyes, the most prevalent complaint was dryness and irritation (18.57%), followed by persistent grittiness (17.14%). 14.29% of patients reported having blurry vision and feeling like they had a foreign body in their eye. Redness, burning, and itching outside were among the other complaints; altogether, dryness-related problems were the most common.

Discussion

The current study validates and extends on prior findings that glucose ingestion causes temporary changes in tear film physiology. Similar to the original study by Abdal et al. (2024), we found a biphasic response, with an initial fall in tear function followed by a return to baseline values. However, while Abdal et al. found a trough in Schirmer scores at 90 minutes after consuming 0.5% glucose, our findings showed that a higher concentration (1.0%) generated more noticeable effects at 60 minutes. This implies that the size and timing of glucose-induced tear film alterations could be dose-dependent.

One major strength of our study is the addition of tear breakup time (TBUT) as a supplemental measure of tear stability. Whereas Abdal et al. (2024) concentrated exclusively on aqueous tear generation using the Schirmer test, our analysis demonstrated that glucose influences both tear volume and stability, offering a more complete picture of ocular surface physiology. The methodological comparability between the two investigations, which includes standardized methods and controlled testing conditions, increases confidence that the findings reflect actual physiological processes rather than experimental artifacts.

Our findings are consistent with prior research indicating that systemic glucose variations, even in euglycemic individuals, can temporarily inhibit tear secretion. Afridi et al. (2024) found no significant difference in the effect of 0.5% versus 1.0% glucose consumption, but our findings suggest modest concentration-related changes in both the size and timing of tear suppression. Taken together, these investigations indicate that glucose has a repeatable biphasic effect on tear film measurements, while the diversity in dose-response correlations merits additional investigation.

Clinically, these findings highlight the need of considering dietary glucose intake when assessing patients with dry eye complaints. The short-lived but significant alterations in tear dynamics seen here suggest that recent carbohydrate ingestion may either aggravate or disguise ocular surface dysfunction. This has practical implications for

clinical practice and research protocols, as standardized pre-test conditions may help reduce variability.

CONCLUSION

The study found that both tear production and tear stability changed significantly over time, declining noticeably at 60 minutes and then gradually increasing again. These changes were verified to be statistically significant by repeated measures ANOVA. According to the results, tear film dynamics change over time and need to be taken into account while conducting clinical evaluations and treatments.

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